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INTRODUCTION

The term concept dates back to 1550–60; from Latin conceptum “something conceived,” originally neuter of conceptus (past participle of concipere), equivalent to con- con- + cep- (variant stem of -cipere, combining form of capere “to seize”) + -tus past participle ending. The notion of the concept began to use widely in linguistic studies since the mid XX century. C. A. Askoldov was one of the first scientist who explored the concept thoroughly. He mentioned in his book that “mental entity that replaces us in the process of thought vague set of objects of the same kind of”.

In this sense, the concept's fundamental cognitive feature acts as a substitute for function. It should be noted that “concept” was used to describe the notion as a synonym. Due to the lexical equivalent of these two words across languages, in our opinion, is synonymous

COGNITIVE FEATURES OF THE CONCEPT “FRIENDSHIP”

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the roots of the notion concept, along with a deep review of the linguistic literature on various ways to describe concepts. In this work, a thorough phased cognitive-conceptual analysis is proposed, in which, depending on the purpose of the study, the principles of conceptual analysis are used, based on the preparation of a cognitive map, on the construction of the concept of nominative fields, and on cognitive interpretation of metaphor. The cognitive features of the concept “friendship” is also discussed via different methods.

with the usage of two terms. The idea of “semantic meaning of the name (sign),” which is defined as “the content of the concept, the volume of which is the object (denotation) of the name,” is taken from the Latin concept's meaning idea.

This definition supports the idea that the concept of nature in terms of new approaches to language learning is different from the meaning of the word and is interdisciplinary in nature, and this, in turn, serves as one of the main provisions contemporary linguistic research. In this regard, the concept has a broader meaning than the concept, and established as an independent and a key term in the studies on the problems of cognitive linguistics, cultural linguistics, psycholinguistics, philosophy of language, communicative linguistics, pragmatic linguistics, i.e., all the linguistic areas, based on the interdisciplinary nature of language learning. However, the identification of the

concept and the concept is not excluded, as some scholars consider these terms as synonyms.

MATERIALS REVIEW

First of all, a concept (abstract term: conception) is a mental symbol, abstract notion, or "unit of knowledge" that is constructed from other units that serve as its qualities. Usually, a notion has a matching representation in a language or symbology, like a single definition for a word. Modern philosophical prevalent ideas make an effort to understand the nature of concepts. While the semantic theory of ideas (originating with Frege's difference between concept and object) maintains that they are abstract things, the representational theory of mind suggests that concepts are mental representations. Though abstract notions may not always conjure up visuals in the mind the way certain thoughts do, they are nonetheless considered to be concepts.

In cognitive linguistics, abstract concepts are transformations of concrete concepts derived from embodied experience. The mechanism of transformation is structural mapping, in which properties of two or more source domains are selectively mapped onto a blended space.

One of the current issues in modern linguistics is the creation of methodologies for researching the notion. Concept is what American linguists refer to as a thinking unit. Conceived as a sophisticated educational and cognitive unit, it represents the linguistic apparatus and creates the semantic space of language, which is investigated using specialized linguistic techniques. The goal of research concepts was to "understand meaning structures, objectify specific properties of

concepts, determine the frequency (typical of many concepts) taxonomic characteristics, and define the characteristics common to these typological qualities investigated concepts." Then, based on them, a generalization of the notion of features was made, along with a choice of conceptual structures and cognitive models of language schemes that really implemented the concept of features that had been researched in the contrasted languages.

The framework of M. Minsky's theory incorporates the roots of conceptual analysis. The methodology is founded on the idea that human perception of reality is carried out by comparing the data structures linked to conceptual objects that are kept in memory and are required to depict a stereotyped scenario, as well as the existing frames in the memory. According to the definition given under the term "frame," it is "a unit of knowledge structured around some concepts, but unlike associations holding the data on the material, typical and possible for this concept," they concretize, which is typical of a particular culture.

The top level of the frame's hierarchical structure is its name, while the lower level is made up of terminals or slots sites that provide details about the given frame and may also contain sub slots or subframes. Slots that explain the research's subject and make clear how it will be used. Subframes interframe specify connections between various mental things that are remembered. As a result, the frame is made up of a variety of slots that are filled with words and connected by other frames to create new slots. This relationship study allows for the presentation of both what is possible and what is impossible for the

future, i.e., it informs the reader about the typical frame of action and follow-up. Cognitive interpretation created typical conditions through frames, which are "packages of knowledge" or information that already exist in memory, implying suitable links between conceptual objects in memory. The language used to identify the conceptual object under study as a complex structure, or frame, in a specific language carrier, is what essentially determines how the research is framed. Afterwards, important terminals or slots that make up a frame structure are identified, associative connections are made, activating these slots, and each slot's modeled conceptual field is then revealed. aspects of the frame's content that are universal and country-specific in each of the languages being compared when comparing different languages.

The relevance of this topic is explained by the fact that in order to understand the cultural specifics of a language, it is necessary, first of all, to analyze the main value orientations, among which, undoubtedly, "friendship" belongs. Interest in the study of its ethnospecific features arose in the light of the anthropocentric reorientation of the paradigm of humanitarian knowledge within the framework of linguoculturology, which studies spiritual meanings in an inseparable unity with their "bodily embodiment". However, unlike such metaphysical entities as love, soul, happiness, the concept of friendship has not been studied (in linguistic comprehension!) in sufficient detail. Some aspects are considered in the works of P. Florensky, A. Vezhbetskaya, Ufimtseva N.V., as well as Pshenina T., Shaimerdinova N.G., Smirnova A.A., Lukashkova O.Yu.

This study touches upon the problems of comparative linguistics, partly philosophy and psychology. Thus, the linguistic reflection of this fragment of a person's cognition of himself in relation to another can become part of the construction of the LCM as a whole and contribute to the study of the ethnosemantic personality in the studied linguocultures.

The scientific novelty of the work lies in the construction of a model of the linguo-cultural concept "friendship" on the basis of materials of various types of discourse in Russian and English, which, in our opinion, allows us to more fully describe the entire paradigm of its verbal implementations. This approach determines the need to develop a specific research methodology that combines the techniques of semantic, functional and formal analysis. In the course of comparison, based on the analysis of the discourse realizations of the concept in the scientific and everyday consciousness of the speakers of the Russian and English languages, first its semantic prototype is formed in its hypostatic realizations in each of them, and only then these invariants are analyzed by the completeness of features and a set of other characteristics and identified their linguistic and cultural features.

The theoretical significance of the dissertation seems to lie in its relevance from the point of view of approaching the problem of the relationship between language and culture, emotions and cognition, displaying in the language of a certain fragment of the value picture of the world. The results obtained are of scientific interest for researchers in such areas of modern linguistics as cognitive linguistics,

psycholinguistics, sociopsycholinguistics, ethnopsycholinguistics, linguoculturology, as well as for specialists dealing with the relationship between language and thinking, language and culture, language and ethnos. In addition, this work has value for linguo-cultural studies of the national specifics of linguocultural concepts and structural features of comparable segments of the conceptsphere of a particular ethnic group, as well as to study the characteristics of the linguistic consciousness of representatives of a certain linguocultural community.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of metaphorical thinking are concepts verbalized by cognitive metaphors or in the terminology of John Lakoff and M.Johnson metaphorical concepts that are found in the deepest foundations of human conceptual systems are assets conceptual framework with which we perceive the objects of one type in terms of objects of a different type, reflection means a more well-known, usually a particular sphere. The metaphor is based on the interaction between the sphere of the source and the target area in which the system of knowledge structures (frames, concepts) the conceptual scope of the source are the basis for modeling the conceptual scope of the target. The source of knowledge that make up the conceptual sphere, is spiritual, cultural, social, linguistic experience of human interaction with the surrounding reality. The cognitive metaphors, according to George Lakoff, so deeply rooted in the human mind, which is often not recognized as a metaphor, as «It is an integral part of the cultural slang age media paradigm», and «the most fundamental cultural values consistent

with the metaphorical structure of the basic concepts of the culture».

Cognitive metaphor in our work determine the content of the concept shaped component, which plays an important concept of the structure, in some cases, the dominant role. In this regard, interest is proposed by Z.D.Popova, I.A.Sternin research methodology shaped the component. These researchers have isolated shaped component of the concept of perceptual and cognitive images. Perceptive image reflects sensory representations that are generated using human senses and include the visual, audible, tactile, olfactory and gustatory images. Cognitive image is represented by semantic and metaphorical concept ties with other concepts, i.e., cognitive metaphor, which is based on personalization and personalizing the name of the concept on the basis of inherent human - moral, emotional evaluation, intellectual, its cultural skills, reflecting the characteristics of metaphorical denotation of the concept.

For the purpose of our work a detailed analysis of the linguistic literature on methods of describing the concept justified by the need to develop its own methodology, methods and techniques of analysis that contribute to the most adequate description of Friendship/Do'stlik/Дружество.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, this work is based on the linguistic perception of concept. It differs from other views, because concept is related to a certain way of its expression in language. Concept is an ideal content, any thinking unit, having the meaning, a complex thinking image, operational

thinking unit verbalized by different means of speech in the process communication.

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